

DEVELOPING THE VOCABULARY OF 5th-6th CLASS PUPILS WITH THE HELP OF CORPUS

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Abstract. *As modern technology advances, corpus-based learning also becomes a useful tool in language teaching, using corpus-based training for teachers and students, as not all English as a language online introductory classes are provided. In addition, teachers are faced with help in obtaining a classroom corpus. They offer a brief overview of the process of reviewing corpora and conducting problems in language learning. Three articles also emphasized the role of the teacher. The researchers then cross-reference some of the material and results into a corpus appropriate for different language levels. The activity helps to develop students' vocabulary and grammatical knowledge.*

Keywords: *corpus, lexical competence, vocabulary.*

According to Varley, technology and computers have become one of the visions of human life. No one can deny that technology has a great impact on people's lifestyles, but according to Breyer (2008), education is one area that has not been strongly influenced by technology. Corpus studies are one of the technology trials that can be very useful in teaching but are still not widely used or conducted.

A corpus is a collection of written or spoken text on a computer. In the past, the term was more associated with a work, such as all the writings of a single author.

Since the advent of the computer, large volumes of text can be stored with the help of analytical tools (O'Keeffe, McCarthy, Carter 2007). An O'Keeffe corpus is a collection of electronic text documents on personal computers.

Since a corpus is stored on a computer, it allows the collection and analysis of large volumes of text using specially designed software. A language can consist of a possible corpus of writing or texts. If it is a corpus of written language, the texts can be checked into the computer by scanning, typing, and retrieving. Recover from files available on the Internet or in electronic form.

For this reason, foreign language classes place a great burden on language classes to acquire vocabulary and develop real language. As Biber, Konrad, and Reppen (2008) point out, another characteristic of a corpus is that it is the principal collection of texts available for qualitative and quantitative analysis. This definition is useful because it covers several important issues.

On the other hand, even if it is produced by using the corpus, it cannot provide lessons to the Internet. Thus, it is possible to load the students' corpus, from the classroom to the teachers.

Salma (2010) states that studies on how English speakers use corpus linguistics to provide corrections for certain language items and phrases were conducted.

Maddalena (2001) explains that with foreign language learners, authentic and real-life examples are more useful than examples that do not resemble real-life language transfer by the teacher.

D. Pulatova (2023) believes that, learners can learn vocabulary that is relevant to their needs and interests, which can increase motivation and engagement in the language learning

process. One of the main benefits of corpus analysis for language learning is the ability to develop personalized language learning activities. By analyzing language data, learners can identify their strengths and weaknesses in terms of language use. This can then be used to develop personalized language learning activities that are tailored to the learner's specific needs and interests.

Another advantage of corpus delivery in language learning is that it allows learners to work with and analyze the language.

Indeed, with the corpus of students learning a foreign language, it is possible to know the meaning, form, and support of national words, as well as from the real language. If a foreign language is taught by setting up a corpus of classrooms, it will be effective in many aspects of student development.

Salma (2010) supported Maddale's view that the teacher plays a crucial role in sending from the corpus in classrooms. In his opinion, for students to benefit from the corpus, the priority of teachers should be post-corpus teaching. According to Breyer, the teacher plays a vital role in loading the corpus in language teaching. Therefore, Breyer examines the teacher's role and teacher-led review in the first corpus of his research.

A language corpus can be used to enhance the classroom experience in several ways. For the teacher, the corpus can be used to improve their understanding of classroom interactions and the language learning process itself. For example, teachers can collect transcripts of classroom activities and analyze them to identify recurring interactions between teachers and students. Alternatively, the summaries written by students can be studied to identify student misbehavior and thereby target instruction to their problem areas. For students, corpora can be used as part of the learning process for specific structures. Students can acquire their vocabulary through corpus dictionaries. However, students can use a learning corpus to learn a foreign language in the classroom. O'Donnell studied that a learner corpus is a corpus of texts (written or spoken) produced by learners of a foreign language. This text written by a non-native speaker should be considered in terms of the writer's mother tongue (native language) and the language in which the text is written (foreign language). In some cases, the learner corpus is limited to a simple native/foreign language combination (eg, English learners of Spanish). In other cases, the learner's corpus may include a wide range of their primary language, but only one foreign language—for example, the ICLE corpus (International Corpus of Learner English, Granger 2003) includes texts written by English language learners in 16 languages.

Research corpus linguistics has been examined by scientific linguists and lexicographers, grammarians, and material writers, and these developments to gain new knowledge about language transfer.

Tomlinson adds that sending from a concordance can influence the language learning process, stimulate interest and speculation in reading, and help the learner develop pattern recognition in the target language, and a common account of this -helps review books. Tomlinson shows five different ways teachers can send their students off the computer-assisted assembly line collection. It is suitable for all do-it-yourself (do-it-yourself) classes because it involves students (beginners) collecting and analyzing language data for themselves. This is especially true in classrooms where people do not have access to technology,

although it is possible that most readers' corporate dictionaries now contain such frequency data, along with natural examples and grammatical information for each meaning of the word. All of the most searched words have different meanings and uses, and each form has a corresponding

pattern for meaning. The dictionary entries for the most common words should contain a lot of useful information, and after they are collected, they should be displayed for attention in the necessary lines. These can be used by teachers and materials production tools before producing production-based activities, and students can qualitatively improve their knowledge of aspects of the word being studied after selecting and completing such productions, although corpora are difficult to carry in language teaching, they have great potential in foreign language classrooms. If teachers are trained to produce corpus-friendly productions, they can help their students learn to load in English by native speakers. Some of the things to consider when developing a product for a corpus include the students' calculations, cultural background, and the age group of the students. Also, recommend from online corpus as they are always available. Corpus is required in the classroom, and foreign language teachers and researchers must be convinced of its needs. The researchers' next plan is to keep some of the above-mentioned productions more deeply colored to warn about the supply, product, and damage of each. Teachers can download from the first pedagogical corpus; students can study online corpus. Thus, the corpus of foreign language teaching in the foreign language class is developing day by day.

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